

Adsorption from Cyclohexane-Benzene Mixtures on Tin Oxide Samples

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Tin oxide gel and tin oxide precipitate have been used for studying preferential adsorption from solutions of cyclohexane and benzene. Both the surfaces take up preferentially cyclohexane indicating that π interactions of benzene with the surface are overpowered by other factors. Interactions between cyclohexane and benzene influence the entire process of adsorption. The composite isotherms with the two oxides have been analysed by the Schay-Nagy and Everett models to give the amounts of individual components in the adsorbed phase. Results show that the adsorbed layer is not even one molecule thick. This has been explained in terms of repulsive forces in cyclohexane-benzene mixtures.

KIPLING and Peakall¹ investigated the adsorption of cyclohexane-benzene mixture on alumina. They found that benzene was adsorbed in preference to cyclohexane and that the surface was completely covered by a monolayer of the liquid mixture. Benzene is preferentially adsorbed from solutions in cyclohexane on the surfaces of Spheron 6, Boehmite, charcoal and graphite². In contrast, it is found that at liquid-vapour interface, cyclohexane is preferentially adsorbed in benzene-cyclohexane system³.

Schay and Nagy^{4,5} utilized the adsorption of this liquid mixture on Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 and carbon to calculate the surface area of these solids. Their results are in good agreement with the results obtained by nitrogen adsorption at low temperature. Similar studies have been made by Kiselov *et al*⁶ on oxidised charcoals and coals which had been treated at high temperatures. Puri *et al*⁷ undertook intensive studies on adsorption from benzene-cyclohexane mixtures on carbons. They studied the influence of carbon-oxygen complexes on the carbon surfaces and reached the conclusion that the preferential adsorption from this liquid mixture is greatly affected by the presence of carbon-oxygen complexes.

Suri and Ramakrishna⁸ made similar studies on chromatographic silica gel. S-shaped isotherms leading to bimolecular thickness were reported by Narang and Ramakrishna⁹ on chromium oxide obtained by the decomposition of ammonium dichromate. Adsorption studies on nickel and nickel oxide from the same system were carried out by Babernics and Teteny¹⁰.

Different models have been used and sometimes compared to analyse the adsorbed layer. Based on his model, Everett¹¹ determined the composition of the adsorbed phase on Spheron 6 in adsorption from this liquid mixture. Suri and Ramakrishna⁸

compared the Schay-Nagy and Everett models for the calculation of n^{σ} i.e. the number of moles in the adsorbed layer. Narang and Ramakrishna⁹ made a comparison of Schay-Nagy and Everett methods to calculate the composition of the adsorbed phase.

Surface activity coefficients i.e. the relative tendencies of the two components to escape from the surface have attracted the attention of some workers in the adsorption studies from benzene-cyclohexane system. Blackburn *et al*¹² carried out studies to determine the surface activity coefficients of the two components on the surface. They used the Elton's convention¹³ that the surface activity of either component and hence its surface activity coefficient is 1 when its surface mole fraction is 1. Since their treatment is not based on any comprehensive model of adsorption and ignores the interfacial tensions, it has been criticised by Everett. Lu and Lama¹⁴ used Everett analysis to investigate the activity coefficients of benzene and cyclohexane on silica gel. Suri and Ramakrishna compared the Schay-Nagy and Everett methods for the determination of surface activity coefficients of these components in adsorption studies on chromatographic silica gel.

Although a number of workers have compared the different theories of adsorption, the studies have remained limited to a few adsorbents. Adsorption studies on large number of adsorbents need be investigated to ascertain the validity of different models for all the liquid mixtures. A perusal of the literature shows that no adsorption studies have been done on tin oxide although it is an important catalyst for oxidation processes and an efficient semiconductor. Adsorption from binary liquid mixtures can lead us to useful information regarding the catalytic and electrical properties of the substance.

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It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the preferential adsorption from cyclohexane-benzene solutions on tin oxide gel and tin oxide precipitate in order to have an idea about the nature of the surface. The temperature of adsorption was 35°. The Schay-Nagy and Everett models of adsorption have been used to find out the composition of the adsorbed phase, thickness of the adsorbed layer and the activity coefficients of the individual components in the adsorbed phase. The method of preparation of solids and measurement of adsorption have been reported earlier^{1,5,16}.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Fig. 1 in the form of plots between $n_0 \Delta x_1 / m$ and x_1 , known as composite isotherms for the binary mixtures. The isotherms are U-shaped indicating that the same component is preferentially adsorbed throughout the concentration range. Cyclohexane is preferentially adsorbed from its solutions in benzene which indicates the non-polar and non-reacting nature of the surfaces.

Fig. 1. Composite isotherms for adsorption from cyclohexane and benzene mixture on tin oxide gel and tin oxide ppt.

● tin oxide gel ; ○ tin oxide ppt

The third column in Table 1 gives the apparent adsorption ($n_0 \Delta x_1 / m$) of cyclohexane calculated from experimental data. Here n_0 is the total

number of moles of the mixture brought into contact with m gram of the adsorbent whereby a change in composition Δx_1 of component 1 of the liquid takes place. K_a in the fifth column is the distribution constant K as given in Everett equation below. The superscript σ refers to the adsorbed phase. x_1 and x_2 stand for the mole fractions of components 1 and 2 in the liquid phase.

$$\frac{x_1 x_2}{n_0 \Delta x_1 / m} = \frac{m}{n^\sigma} \left(x_1 + \frac{1}{K-1} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

The sixth column in Table 1 gives the total number of moles in the adsorbed phase, n_1^σ , calculated by plotting a graph between $x_1 x_2 / (n_0 \Delta x_1 / m)$ and x_1 . The slope and the intercept of the line thus obtained lead us to the values of n^σ . The seventh column gives the corresponding values obtained by the intercept method of Schay and Nagy^{4,5}.

Table 2 gives the composition of the adsorbed phase at various values of x_1 i.e. the mole fraction of component 1 in the liquid phase. The third column in this table gives the mole fraction of cyclohexane in the adsorbed phase. The fourth and the fifth columns give the number of m moles of cyclohexane and benzene, respectively obtained by using eq (2).

$$n_0 \Delta x_1 / m = n^\sigma (x_1^\sigma - x_1) / m \quad \dots (2)$$

$$n_0 \Delta x_1 / m = n_1^\sigma x_2 - n_2^\sigma x_1 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\frac{n_1^\sigma}{(n_1^\sigma)_m} + \frac{n_2^\sigma}{(n_2^\sigma)_m} = t \quad \dots (4)$$

n_1 and n_2 denote the number of moles of components 1 and 2 in the adsorbed phase. $(n_1^\sigma)_m$ and $(n_2^\sigma)_m$ represent monolayers values for the two components on the surface. The sixth and the seventh columns give the corresponding values obtained by eqs. (3-4). The value of t , i.e. the thickness of the adsorbed layer is calculated by dividing n^σ (obtained by Schay-Nagy's extrapolation method) by the monolayer values of cyclohexane on the adsorbents. The molecular areas of the adsorbates¹⁷ and the surface areas on the solids are given in Table 4.

TABLE 1—ADSORPTION FROM BINARY MIXTURES OF CYCLOHEXANE (1)+BENZENE (2) AT 35°

Adsorbent	x_1	$n_0 \Delta x_1 / m$ (m mole/g)	$\frac{x_1 x_2}{n_0 \Delta x_1 / m}$	K_a	n^σ (Everett) (m mole)	n^σ (Schay-Nagy) Intercept method (m mole)				
Tin oxide gel	0.1	0.06	1.5	3.73	0.333	0.2				
	0.2	0.09	1.8							
	0.3	0.10	2.1							
	0.4	0.10	2.4							
	0.6	0.075	3.2							
	0.8	0.045	3.5							
	0.9	0.025	3.6							
	Tin oxide ppt	0.1	0.040				2.2	3.7	0.21	0.14
		0.2	0.055				3.0			
0.3		0.065	3.2							
0.4		0.065	3.7							
0.6		0.055	4.3							
0.8		0.030	5.3							
0.9		0.015	6.0							

TABLE 2—EVERETT AND SCHAY-NAGY ANALYSES OF ADSORPTION FROM MIXTURES OF CYCLOHEXANE (1) AND BENZENE (2) AT 35°

Adsorbent	x_1	x_1^σ (Everett)	Number of m mole in the adsorbed layer (Everett)		Number of m mole in the adsorbed layer (Schay-Nagy)	
			n_1^σ	n_1	n_1^σ	n_2^σ
			Tin oxide gel	0.1	0.3	0.10
	0.2	0.45	0.15	0.18	0.13	0.07
	0.3	0.6	0.20	0.13	0.16	0.04
	0.4	0.69	0.23	0.10	0.18	0.02
	0.6	0.83	0.28	0.05	0.19	0.01
	0.8	0.93	0.31	0.02	0.20	0.01
	0.9	0.97	0.32	0.01	0.20	0.01
Tin oxide ppt.	0.1	0.3	0.07	0.14	0.06	0.09
	0.2	0.48	0.10	0.11	0.08	0.07
	0.3	0.61	0.13	0.08	0.10	0.05
	0.4	0.70	0.15	0.06	0.12	0.02
	0.6	0.85	0.18	0.03	0.14	0.01
	0.8	0.94	0.19	0.02	0.15	0.01
	0.9	0.97	0.20	0.01	0.15	0.01

TABLE 3—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF CYCLOHEXANE AND BENZENE IN THE ADSORBED PHASE ON TIN OXIDE GEL CALCULATED BY THE EVERETT METHOD

	Mole fraction of cyclohexane in the liquid phase (x_1) at equilibrium						
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.9
x_2	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.1
$x_1 r_1$ (C_6H_{12})	0.15	0.24	0.33	0.41	0.58	0.76	0.85
$x_2 r_2$ (C_6H_6)	0.85	0.76	0.67	0.59	0.42	0.24	0.15
x_1^σ (C_6H_{12})	0.30	0.45	0.60	0.69	0.83	0.93	0.97
x_2^σ (C_6H_6)	0.70	0.55	0.40	0.31	0.17	0.07	0.03
$\ln \frac{x_1^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1}$	0.8874	0.9521	1.136	1.174	1.243	1.434	1.780
$x_1^\sigma \ln \frac{x_1^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1}$	0.2662	0.4285	0.6816	0.8032	1.0800	1.3350	1.7280
$\int_0^{x_1^\sigma} \ln \frac{x_1^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1} dx_1^\sigma$	0.2365	0.3735	0.5260	0.6250	0.7915	0.9235	0.9865
$\ln r_1^\sigma$	0.1863	0.1468	0.0636	0.0582	0.0412	0.0201	0.0041
$\ln r_2^\sigma$	0.0297	0.0550	0.1556	0.1782	0.2885	0.4115	0.7415
r_1^σ	1.208	1.158	1.066	1.060	1.042	1.020	1.004
r_2^σ	1.030	1.056	1.168	1.195	1.334	1.509	2.099

TABLE 4—MOLECULAR AREA OF THE ADSORBATE MOLECULES AND MONOLAYER VALUES

Adsorbent	Surface area m ² /g	Adsorbate	Molecular area Å ²	Monolayer value m mole/g
Tin oxide gel	160	Benzene	40	0.65
		Cyclohexane	45	0.58
Tin oxide ppt.	100	Benzene	same	0.41
		Cyclohexane	as above	0.365

Everett eq. (5).

$$\ln r_2^\sigma = x_1^\sigma \ln \frac{(x_1^\sigma x_2 r_2)}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1} - \int_0^{x_1^\sigma} \frac{\ln(x_1^\sigma x_2 r_2) dx_1^\sigma}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1} \dots (5)$$

For the calculation of surface activity coefficients, graphical integration has been carried out. The activity coefficients in the liquid phase r_1 and r_2 were calculated from the vapour-pressure data reported in the literature¹⁰. x_1^σ and x_2^σ values are obtained by the Everett method¹¹.

Table 3 gives the surface activity coefficients r_1^σ and r_2^σ of cyclohexane and benzene calculated by

Both tin oxide gel and tin oxide ppt. prefer cyclohexane from cyclohexane-benzene mixtures. It appears that the surface prefers aliphatic rather than aromatic adsorbates. The maximum values of $n_0 \Delta x/m$ for adsorption from cyclohexane-benzene system are 0.1 and 0.065 m mole, respectively for tin oxide gel and tin oxide precipitate. These values are in proportion to the surface areas of the solids (160 m²/g for SnO₂ gel and 100 m²/g for SnO₂ ppt.). Similarly, the n^0 values for the two solids obtained by the Everett method and Schay-Nagy method are in the ratio of their surface areas. But the values do not seem to correspond to full surface coverage of the solids. Keeping in view the molecular area of cyclohexane as 45 Å², the monolayer values should be 0.58 m mole for tin oxide gel and 0.36 m mole for tin oxide ppt. whereas the Everett values of n^0 are 0.33 and 0.21 m mole, respectively. Thus, a little over half of the surface is covered by the adsorbate. This rules out the possibility of strong surface-adsorbate interactions and reserves only weak physical or van der Waals forces between the surface and the adsorbate. Schay-Nagy method, however, gives still smaller values of the number of moles in the adsorbed phase.

Smaller values than the monolayer capacity in the case of adsorption from cyclohexane-benzene mixture are explicable in terms of the surface activity coefficients of the components in adsorbed phase. It is seen from Table 3 that the Everett values of activity coefficients of both the components are more than one throughout the concentration range and for every composition of the adsorbed phase. While the activity coefficient of cyclohexane decreases from 1.2 to 1.0, that of the benzene rises from 1.0 to 2.1 as we cover the whole concentration range. Near the middle of the concentration range, however, the adsorbed phase appears to be behaving ideally with unit activity coefficient for both the components.

An activity coefficient of more than unity implies repulsive molecular interactions between the two

types of molecules making their co-existence thinner. Hence, the amount of the components in the adsorbed phase is smaller than that can be accommodated on the surface.

The discrepancy in Schay-Nagy analysis in the cyclohexane-benzene system is perhaps due to uncertainty in the orientation of cyclohexane on the surface.

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